
Swami Dayananda Social Reformer and a Sculptor of Humanity

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Abstract:

When educated youth of India were imitating the shallow facets of European civilization and were agitating to plant the growing seeds of England in Indian soil, irrespective of the talent and culture of the Indian people, Swami Dayanand, the biggest apostles of Indo-Aryan civilization remained as a legendary figure of the most advanced ideas in socio-political spheres in India. His incarnation on the earth remained fruitful because he eradicated many evil rituals, rites, practices and traditions which were prevalent in India at that time. Swami Dayanand raised his voice against idol worshipping, fatalism, caste system, ritualism, intoxication, sati tradition, child marriage and many more. Keeping in view the domination of the Vedas and the Hindus, he raised his voice against the degraded practices of Islam and Christianity also and further took the side of the Sandhi Movement to reorganize other sects of the Hindu sect. Swami Dayanand expressed political views about the principles of the state, the form of the governments, functions, rules of law, etc. The special emphasis of this paper is to evaluate and to do justice with his ideology. Further, it seeks to peep into Swami Dayanand's personal life and know him closely as a man of Sacred Vedic Dharma. He brought radical changes in the society but he had to sacrifice his life for it.

Keywords: Swami Dayanand, Arya Samaj, Sati Tradition, Hypocrisy, Brahmanism, The Vedas.

Introduction:

Swami Dayanand Saraswati was born in Tankara village in Gujarat on February 12, 1824. His father's name was Lalji Tiwari and his mother's name was Yashodabai. His life can be better understood from three stages of his life: childhood in home (1824-45), as a disciple, student and reader (1846-69) and (from 1870 to 1883 till his death). His childhood name was Mool Shankar because he was born in the Mool Nakshtra. He was born in a Brahmin family and his father was a follower of Lord Shiva. This family was deeply attached with the Hindu religious notions and as is in common practice in a

Brahmin family, he was told to observe fast and pray to Lord Shiva. His father always told the importance of God to him. When he was eight years old his Upanayana Sanskar was performed and it can be called his formal entry in the field of education. He was told to observe fast and worship Lord Shiva.

He learnt Sanskrit from his father who had profound knowledge of the Vedas. He was merely fourteen years at the time when he had observed the fast on the day of Shiv Ratri. At night, the other members of the family who were doing fast went to sleep but Mool Shankar wanted to know the worth of this fast. Suddenly a mouse comes there and it starts eating the

Prasad or offerings and Mool shankar observed that the Lord Shiva is not doing anything to ward off the mouse. He came to the conclusion that there is no power in the idol, and he is merely wasting his time. He thought that Lord Shiva does not have power to do anything and he thought how can Lord Shiva protect the entire world when he cannot protect his offerings from a mouse? After this incidence, he became against the idol worshipping. Mool Shankar's younger sister died when he was merely sixteen-year-old. He was much attached with his sister and this death breaks him. Unfortunately, his uncle died due to Cholera after some time and Swami Dayanand was immensely disturbed at the loss of his near and dear ones. He had never known that death is the ultimate reality of life. These two incidents had great impact on mind of a young Mool shankar.

He started asking questions about death and why it happens. His questions put his parent's in problem and they thought that they should marry him so that he may entangle in the worldly life. He was engaged soon but his mind was elsewhere. By now he has made up his mind that he would know the cause of death and he would do something so that he may get rid of birth and death. This thinking did not keep him at home and finally he left for sanyas at the age of twenty-one. He went to the Himalayas where he tried to get questions from the other saints but he remained unsatisfied from the answers. Ultimately he reached Mathura where he met Swami Virajanand Dandeesha. Swami Virajanand was a very strict Teacher and he wanted to make his Disciples perfect spiritual person. Mool shankar told the purpose of his life to his spiritual guru that he wanted to attain spiritual enlightenment. His quest to attain supreme knowledge impressed his Guru and in a short span of time Mool shankar became

his most beloved disciple. There is an interesting story regarding both. One day Swami Vrijanand beat Mool shankar very badly with his hand but Mool shankar remained silent and suffered this pain very silently and solemnly.

Educational Philosophy:

The philosophy of Maharishi Dayanand Saraswati can be known from his three famous contributions namely "Satyarth Prakash", "Veda Bhashya Bhumika" and "Veda Bhashya". Further the journal "Arya Patrika" edited by him also reflects his thought. He has devoted two chapters (2nd and 3rd) of the "Satyarth Prakash" to the subject of education for the infants as well as the adolescents. Besides establishing his reputation as a prolific writer, above works indicate his role as an educational and religious reformer. Swami Dayanand Saraswati also criticizes the present education system. He said this system failed to deliver. It is not producing good student. An educated person was supposed to be modest and bear good character. He was required to have control over speech and mind, be energetic, respectful to parents, teachers, Elders and guest, to follow the Nobel path and to shun evil ways, to enjoy the company of the learned people and to be liberal in making gifts. He wrote booklet called as "Vyavharbhanu". In this book he delineated the qualities of a pandit learned person who was entitled to teach and contrasted them with the character of a fool who should not to be entrusted with the education of the children. Swami Dayanand is not composed of a superficial knowledge of three or four subjects as unfortunately it happens to be the case at present, but it covers a wide range of subjects beginning with grammar, literature, the Vedas, Upanishads, Ramayana, Mahabharat and Ayurveda, the Science of health; Dhanurveda, the Science

of war; Gandharvaveda, Aesthetic arts; Arthaveda, Vocational training, Astronomy, Algebra, Arithmetic, Geology, Space science etc. His was certainly a scheme of broad-based foundational education. As for the medium of education, both of this personality have different idea Dayanand, chose to write his works in the lingua franca of India, which he termed as the Aryabhasha, so that his message could reach the masses. Language, apparently, to him was the medium, the vehicle of communication of knowledge and principles of healthy and Dharmic. Same time he also advocacy of Sanskrit but did not supported the English while Swamiji is put great emphasis on mother tongue is the right medium for social or mass education; he prescribes the learning of English and Sanskrit also. While English is necessary for mastering Western science and technology, Sanskrit leads one into the depths of our vast store of classics. The implication is that if language does not remain the privilege of a small class of people, social unity will March forward unhampered.

Social Ideas:

He was against idol worship, caste system, ritualism, fatalism, infanticide, sale of grooms etc. he also stood for the liberation of women and upliftment of depressed class. Keeping in mind the supremacy of Vedas and Hindus, he opposed Islam and Christianity and advocated for Suddhi movement to reconvert the other sects to Hindu order. Swami Dayanand Saraswati sincerely believed that through the spread of Vedic education the urge of regeneration of Indian society could be met. The gurukulas, Girl's Gurukulas and DAV colleges were the most significant contribution of Dayananda. In fact the efforts of Swami Dayanananda freed the people from the clutches of western

education. Dayananda Saraswati also contributed to the growth of democracy and national awakening. It is said that "political independence was one of the first objectives of Dayanand. Indeed he was the first man to use the term Swaraj." He was the first to insist on people to use only swadeshi things manufactured in India and to discard the foreign things. He was the first to recognize Hindi as national language of India." Dayanand Saraswati was the strong votary of democracy and self government. He declared that good Government was no substitute for self-government. He paid utmost attention to the regeneration of rural India. In many ways Dayanand anticipated Mahatma Gandhi in his constructive programme. His Arya Samaj was constituted through the procedure of democratic election from the below to bottom. Swami Dayanand represented a transitional stage and inaugurated future developments with his vision of a complete overhaul of Hindu Society through education.

Conclusion:

Dayanand was fully convinced that the nation cannot prosper unless education spreads. But our education system should not be a mere carbon copy of the western type of education. There should be a law to compel the parents to send every boy or girl who is eight years old to school. Every boy and every girl should be sent to Gurukulas where they stay with their gurus. There should be separate Gurukulas for boys and girls. The King's son and the farmer's son should be equals in a Gurukula. They should all be made to work alike. The Gurukula should be situated far from the town and the city, and should enjoy calm and serenity. Our culture and our great books like the Vedas should be introduced to our students. Side by side, mathematics, geology, astronomy and other sciences which are important in

modern life should also be taught. Swamy Dayanand founded gurukulas at various places to fulfil these objects. Among them Kangadi is famous even to this day. Swami Dayanand Saraswati is one the most important reformers and spiritual forces India has known in recent times. The dominant personality of Dayanand Saraswati had found extraordinary reflection in the virility of the Arya Samaj movement, and in almost every one of its adherents. The contribution of Arya Samaj in the field of education is commendable. The establishment of education institutions, particularly in the northern and eastern parts of India, and the formation of the Gurukula Academy at Hardwar exemplify the very rightful eagerness of many Samajists to revive the ancient ideal and traditions of Hindu education. The

members of Arya Samaj movement are also in the forefront of other public services of the country. This is evident from the number of members of the Samaj who have attained public eminence and have won the gratitude of the Indian nation. The contribution and importance of Swami Dayananda will remain alive in the country so long as the Arya Samaj exists and continues its activities of religious and social reforms.

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